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Project website address: <http://fastprk2.eu/>

***Deliverable 4.1- Prototype Demonstration and Field Trial
Results***

A. Dissemination Level

PU	Public
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

B. Document details

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0. Executive Summary

Fastprk2 develops a smart on-street parking system to control regulated parking spots with occupancy sensors, aiming to improve the user experience and the parking area management in Europe.

This deliverable provides the **overview of the work done** over recent months (M15-M21) towards the **implementation of the pilot campaign** foreseen in the EC-GA, and consequently, gather sufficient evidence to validate in real scenarios the new technology developed in the project.

In this document, the high-level description of the Fastprk2 prototype deployments at different European locations are provided, showing tangible evidence that the tests are successfully running in real-life conditions for the time being. Nevertheless, the **full details** of the obtained results and the valuable feedback received from the different stakeholders will be **set out in the deliverable D5.1**, after the final product is tested and ready for the market launch.

This report has been submitted to the EC with a delay of some months. This deviation has been duly communicated to the PO in due time. The underlying reason is that pilots' campaigns of parking systems have been subject to many challenges, which can be barely controlled by an SME company like Worldsensing, such as adverse weather conditions, political decisions involving delays in granting installation permits and production incidences. Following a conservative strategy, a longer time window for the tests campaign and the analysis of the results has, therefore, been considered necessary as a direct and effective risk mitigation measure. This decision does not jeopardize the achievement of the project objectives fixed at the beginning of the action.

Since the deliverable is labelled as "*Demonstrator*" in the EC-GA, Worldsensing provides here direct evidence of the attained results through a set of images and operational details of each pilot venue.

1. Introduction

Fastprk2 develops a leading end-to-end solution with advanced features compared to the competitors' solutions. To make full use of the potential of the project efforts, the improved functionalities of the new product range from the certified parking occupancy detection to advanced services offered to end-users, merging the solution with the mobility platform of Worldsensing.

The Fastprk2 project seeks to develop a complex system that involves hardware and software development, which has been designed to enrich the product portfolio of Worldsensing but keeping at all times the equilibrium between the technological breakthroughs and the commercial priorities.

In this deliverable, Worldsensing presents evidence of (i) **the groundwork leading to the pilot deployment in real-life scenarios** outside the lab, (ii) **the effort to complete the equipment installation at different European venues** and (iii) a brief technical **description of the pilots' characteristics** which are successfully running.

From a practical point of view and unlike the established work plan in the EC-GA, the activities of WP4 and WP5 have finally merged in an iterative process to dynamically improve the very first releases of the Fastprk2 prototypes towards the successful achievement of the final product.

In fact, the varying maturity levels of the elements within the Fastprk2 architecture has made advisable adopting this strategy.

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 2.** Description of the pilot project campaign, the applicable ethical constraints and the previous steps necessary to the actual Fastprk2 deployment implementation stage. For more details, please refer to deliverable D7.1 as a supporting document to understand the global context.
- **Section 3.** Pilots deployment description at different European venues, with full details of the operational infrastructure running at the time of this writing, and specific details about the installation actions.
- **Section 4.** Preliminary assessment of the obtained test results. Further details will be provided in the deliverable D5.1 with the complete analysis of the work done and the main lessons-learned to effectively push the market launch of the final solution in the coming months.
- **Section 5.** Wrap-up and main conclusions.

This document is a review of intensive and multifaceted work involving many different departments within the company. For this reason, it is almost impossible to provide full details of each development without a tedious and long wording. On the contrary, and since the deliverable is labelled as "Demonstrator" in the EC-GA, Worldsensing provides here direct evidence of the attained results through a set of images and operational details of each pilot venue. **Further details are available upon request.**

From a reporting point of view, the present status of the tasks and associated milestones listed in the EC-GA is summarized in the table below.

Table 1 - Status of the project tasks and milestones linked to the pilots at present time

WP	Task	Comment	Milestone	Status
4	T4.1 Robust parking management prototype in specific versions	Architecture defined in WP3 can be easily accommodated to specific requirements from the customers	MS7 TRL7 operational tests results	Completed
	T4.2 Modules dependency	The dependency between the different modules and data sources has been defined and validated in lab-controlled demos		
	T4.3 Complexity analysis and policies definition	Set of policies and rules to assess the real deployments, the expected functionalities and the hardware and software needs have been drafted. To be refined in WP5		
5	T5.1 Field configuration for pilot deployment	Preparatory actions for each pilot trial have been completed	MS8 TRL8 operational tests results	On-track
	T5.2 Product quality demonstration	Tests running in real-scenarios. Direct interaction with stakeholders. Full details to be provided in D5.1		
	T5.3 Solution assessment			

2. Pilots project campaign: description and groundwork

Fastprk2 is a market-oriented project which will **result in a technology ready for commercialization at M24**. To achieve this goal, the final solution must be previously validated in real-test scenarios, aiming to achieve in advance the TRL8 status with proven guarantees. With this in mind, a detailed solution assessment involving technical and commercial aspects is advisable and it is being performed for the time being.

According to the EC-GA provisions, an intense piloting campaign in different European venues has been envisaged with a three-faceted objective:

1. **Gathering real data** to improve the technical implementation of the final product release.
2. Acquiring the necessary **know-how to guarantee the replicability** of the proposed solution for different environments.
3. Raise the **awareness of the solution** by the future clients and receiving a detailed assessment of its performance.

Worldsensing has, therefore, a **unique opportunity to test the effectiveness of the project results** and receive an enriching **feedback from stakeholders** before the product launch.

The stakeholders engaged to support the project pilots (*Table 2*) have been selected for their complementary background, combining developers of mobility management technologies, trading companies of smart-parking solutions and public and private end-users. This will allow Worldsensing acquiring a representative overview of the strengths and weaknesses of Fastprk2 solution from different but complementary perspectives.

Table 2 – Fastprk2 pilots during the validation phase

Pilot #	Stakeholder	Venue	# Sensors
1	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)	Barcelona (Spain)	12
2	ENGIE- Cofely Fabricom	Antwerp (Belgium)	24
3	SWARCO	Wattens (Austria)	47
4	AFAPARK	Paris (France)	6
5	City Parking Group S.A.	Gdynia (Poland)	

As described in the deliverables D3.1 and D3.2, **Fastprk2 architecture is modular and adaptable**. Therefore, each specific pilot has required an accommodation process to offer the desired functionalities that the end-user seeks. In fact, all pilots

supported by the project share the concept 1 of Fastprk2 (improved parking detection) while concept 2 (parking management platform) and concept 3 (ITS) has been adapted to the specific needs in an interactive process with the stakeholders (tasks T4.1 and T5.1).

The fifth pilot in Poland is one of the first commercial opportunities for Fastprk2. For this reason, it is the last one in the implementation queue. At this moment, the final scope has not yet been decided, and what elements will be supported by the EU funds and the clients is under discussion with the client. To avoid any needles inconsistency in the reporting to the EC, the final details of this pilot will be provided in the deliverable D5.1.

Fastprk2 pilots in the frame of the EC action will exclusively check with real data the attainment of **Concept 1**, while the rest of functionalities (**Concept 2 & Concept 3**) will be evaluated by using **simulated data**¹.

Worldsensing is committed to perform a professional management of ethical issues potentially emerging in the scope of the pilots. The company already identified relevant ethical concerns during the preparation of the EC-GA, and simultaneously, the EC carried out an ethics scrutiny of the proposal, with the objective of verifying the respect of ethical principles and the relevant legislation. With regard to Fastprk2, the research entails specific ethical implications, involving human subjects. In this context, the pilots' deployments have been designed according to the ethical provisions summarized in the deliverable D7.1

Fastprk2 involves work with humans. **Two different kind of end-users** will be engaged in the project pilots to validate the functionalities provided by the Fastprk2 solution: **citizens and technology/commercial stakeholders**.

As regards the former, it must be pointed out that the detection mechanism of the parking spots does not entail any personal data, but the physical detection of vehicles without the identification of the citizens' identity in any case. For this reason, anonymous data are used only for statistical and predictive purposes, and they are integrated into the platform on an aggregated level.

With the aim to avoid any controversy about the consent of citizens to participate in **Fastprk2, the tests' areas have been clearly identified using a public notice** whose content has been agreed with the local authorities on a case-by-case basis. This point is explicitly stated in the agreement with the pilots' managers in line with the EC-GA provisions (Annex V). In this way, citizens (drivers and pedestrians) always know in advance that they take part in the pilot study, implicitly consenting their participation in Fastprk2 when they choose a parking spot in the pilot area.

On the other hand, the implementation of enforcement tools has been redesigned from its initial conception: Worldsensing proposes an alarm system so that local authorities move a supervisor to punish the offender on-spot if necessary. The identification of law violators directly through Fastprk2 technology is beyond the scope of the project and may collide with National legal regulations. Details of the enforcement service are given in the deliverable D3.1.

¹ ITS services tested in the pilots are operated with simulated and synthetic data. Only the traffic monitoring tool may use real data provided by a third party (TomTom) through a public API. In this particular case, Worldsensing does not receive any information from users, but aggregated information of the traffic flow per street.

Fastprk2 will allow the **data storage of parking events without the identification of citizens** and the individual life style patterns.

Regarding the technology stakeholders, they are expected to provide feedback about the pilot results. Despite this will be done at institutional level, Worldsensing will keep a direct contact with physical persons (employees) to gather the information.

Table 3 - Detail of H-requirements for citizens and pilots' stakeholders

End-users	Recruitment	Identification	Informed Consent	
			Procedure	Template
Citizens	Open and random	Anonymous	Public notice in the street	Pilot dependent
Technology/commercial stakeholders	Selected for their profile	Table 2	Pilot agreement with WS	Annex V

Personal data such as name, mail and telephone will be handled according to the applicable legislation on Data Protection.

In this sense, Worldsensing will act to comply with the regulations on Personal Data protection at National level. The fine details of the actions taken in this subject will be provided in the final Periodic Report of the project.

3. Pilots deployment: operational details

In this chapter, the main characteristics of each project pilot, except the Polish one, are presented in a catch-eye approach, trying to summarize their scope. Images of the installed sensors and the pilots' venues are provided in the corresponding annexes of the deliverable.

Pilot 1: UPC (Barcelona, Spain)

Third Party General Details	Institution / Company	Universitat Politècnica de Barcelona (UPC)
	Main contact point	
	Other contacts done to implement the deployment (i.e. teleconf, visits on premises, etc)	

Location Details	Venue (address and geographic coordinates)	UPC Calle Jordi Girona, 31 08034 Barcelona (Spain) GPS coordinates: 41.3889784344569,2.1138623938485956
	Google maps images and photos of the area (+ sign)	See Annex 1
	Infrastructure details	
	Number of sensors	12
	Number of gateways	1
	Number of other physical elements (PC, Server, etc)	Own resources from the Third Party

Installation Details	Company in charge	<p>Worldsensing pays for the installation.</p> <p>Installer: <i>Ciurans Group SCP</i> <i>Avda. Can Prat, 20</i> <i>08100 Mollet del Vallès (BCN)</i> <i>CIG J61898227</i> <i>Tel. +34 931988282</i> <i>info@microzanjas.com</i></p> <p>The installer is an official provider selected by WS internal purchase procedures</p>
	Images of the installation process and the final result	See Annex 1

Operational Details	Services to be tested	Parking Occupancy Prediction
		Sustainable Traffic Model
		Anomaly Detector Service
	Evidence of the normal operation	See Annex 1
	Duration of the pilot programme	5 months

Pilot 2: ENGIE (Antwerp, Belgium)

Third Party General Details	Institution / Company	ENGIE
	Main contact point	
	Other contacts done to implement the deployment (i.e. teleconf, visits on premises, etc)	

Location Details	Venue (address and geographic coordinates)	Antwerp downtown: Van Wesenbekestraat 2060 Antwerpen, Belgium GPS coordinates: 51.220222, 4.420752
	Google maps images and photos of the area (+ sign)	See Annex 2
	Infrastructure details	
	Number of sensors	24
	Number of gateways	1
	Number of other physical elements (PC, Server, etc)	Own resources from the Third Party

Installation Details	Company in charge	Worldsensing pays for the installation. Installer: Engie Kontichsesteenweg 25 – 2630 Aartselaar - BELGIUM The installer is directly the client (third party partner).
	Images of the installation process and the final result	See Annex 1

Operational Details	Services to be tested	Traffic Forecasting
		Parking Occupancy Prediction
		Multimodal Service
		Guidance and Recommendation Service
		Sustainable Traffic Model
		Anomaly Detector Service
	Evidence of the normal operation	See Annex 2
	Duration of the pilot programme	5 months

Pilot 3: SWARCO (Wattens, Austria)

Third Party General Details	Institution / Company	SWARCO AG
	Main contact point	
	Other contacts done to implement the deployment (i.e. teleconf, visits on premises, etc)	

Location Details	Venue (address and geographic coordinates)	SWARCO premises: Blattenwaldweg 8 6112 Wattens, Austria GPS coordinates: 47.288276, 11.587236
	Google maps images and photos of the area (+ sign)	See Annex 3
	Infrastructure details	
	Number of sensors	47
	Number of gateways	1
	Number of other physical elements (PC, Server, etc)	Own resources from the Third Party

Installation Details	Company in charge	<p>Worldsensing pays for the installation.</p> <p>Installer:</p> <p>P&O di des of Perkmann Geom. Georg Linee guide a led via Constantino, 4 Konstantinerweg Nr. 4 39050 Fie allo Sciliar Völs am Schlern (Italy)</p>
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		<p>The installer has been selected by the client (third party partner) following its internal procurement rules.</p>
	Images of the installation process and the final result	See Annex 3

Operational Details	Services to be tested	Parking Occupancy Prediction
		Guidance and Recommendation Service
		Sustainable Traffic Model
		Anomaly Detector Service
	Evidence of the normal operation	See Annex 3
	Duration of the pilot programme	3 months

Pilot 4: AFAPARK (Paris, France)

Third Party General Details	Institution / Company	AFAPARK
	Main contact point	
	Other contacts done to implement the deployment (i.e. teleconf, visits on premises, etc)	▪

Location Details	Venue (address and geographic coordinates)	AFAPARK Parc D'activité de a Gare Rue Louise Michel 95570 Bouffémont - France GPS N49.044141 E2.321854 www.afapark.com
	Google maps images and photos of the area (+ sign)	See Annex 4
	Infrastructure details	
	Number of sensors	6
	Number of gateways	1
	Number of other physical elements (PC, Server, etc)	Own resources from the Third Party

Installation Details	Company in charge	Worldsensing pays for the installation. Installer: Microzanjas The installer is a regular provider of Worldsensing selected following the internal procurement rules of Worldsensing
	Images of the installation process and the final result	See Annex 4

Operational Details	Services to be tested	Parking Occupancy Prediction
		Guidance and Recommendation Service
		Sustainable Traffic Model
		Anomaly Detector Service
	Evidence of the normal operation	See Annex 4
	Duration of the pilot programme	3 months

4. Pilots deployment: rationale

The pilots' locations have been carefully thought out to build sufficient knowledge on the operation of Fastprk2 technology. The table 4 summarizes the main reasons to select these concrete pilots and the level of difficulty to test Fastprk2 therein.

Table 4 - Reasons to select the pilots' locations (chronological order)

Location	Reason	Scenario (difficulty)
Barcelona	1. Proximity to Worldsensing (Barcelona)	Easy
	2. Facilities for the first proofs	
	3. Controlled area (no road traffic)	
Antwerp	1. Urban area	Critical
	2. Electromagnetic noise (nearby tram traffic)	
	3. Commercial contact with ENGIE	
Paris	1. Controlled area in a partner with expertise in parking exploitation	Medium
	2. Opportunity to compare Fastpr2 vs Fastprk	
Wattens	1. Extreme weather conditions	High
	2. Feedback from a direct competitor	
Gdynia	1. Commercial opportunity	

As discussed earlier, the associated services to each pilot deployment have been tailored to the third-party requirements. The following tables present the status of each pilot:

ITS (Service)		Barcelona		Rationale
		Y	N	
1	Traffic Forecasting		X	Location at university campus without road traffic
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X		Location at a loading / unloading area. The service will provide useful insight to delivery trucks
3	Multimodal Service		X	Parking spots used by freight companies. Consequently, the possibility to leverage on the public transportation does not apply herein
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service		X	No DMS available
5	Automatic Payment Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
6	Automatic Enforcement Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X		UPC is environmentally conscious, and they appreciate having this service in the pilot
8	Dynamic Pricing Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X		Service installed by default to operate the Fastprk2 platform

ITS (Service)		Antwerp		Rationale
		Y	N	
1	Traffic Forecasting	X		The pilot is installed in downtown with severe road traffic problems. The service is particularly useful in this location
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X		Location in a mixed area with loading areas and regular parking spots. The service will provide useful information to the city operator
3	Multimodal Service	X		Location in downtown. End-users may be interested in combining private- and public transportation
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service	X		The local partner in charge of the installation are manufacturers/installers of DMS panels. A commercial opportunity may arise
5	Automatic Payment Service		X	Service not requested by the pilot partner

6	Automatic Enforcement Service		X	Service already in place with the partner's own solution
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X		Service installed by default in urban locations to rise the environmental awareness
8	Dynamic Pricing Service		X	Service not requested by the pilot partner
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X		Service installed by default to operate the Fastprk2 platform

Wattens				
ITS (Service)		Y	N	Rationale
1	Traffic Forecasting		X	In-door traffic area without road traffic.
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X		Service requested by the pilot partner
3	Multimodal Service		X	Service not requested by the pilot partner
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service	X		Service requested by the pilot partner
5	Automatic Payment Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
6	Automatic Enforcement Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X		Service installed by default in urban locations to rise the environmental awareness
8	Dynamic Pricing Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X		Service installed by default to operate the Fastprk2 platform

Paris				
ITS (Service)		Y	N	Rationale
1	Traffic Forecasting		X	In-door traffic area without road traffic.
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X		Service requested by the pilot partner
3	Multimodal Service		X	Service not requested by the pilot partner
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service	X		Service requested by the pilot partner
5	Automatic Payment Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
6	Automatic Enforcement Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X		Service installed by default in urban locations to rise the environmental awareness
8	Dynamic Pricing Service		X	The parking spots are of free use
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X		Service installed by default to operate the Fastprk2 platform

Gdynia				
ITS (Service)		Y	N	Rationale
1	Traffic Forecasting	X		This pilot may become a final commercial opportunity beyond Fastprk2 action implementation. Besides, it is the last in the implementation queue. For this reason, the final versions of all the services will be tested in a real-environment. Prototype of TRL9
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X		
3	Multimodal Service	X		
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service	X		
5	Automatic Payment Service	X		
6	Automatic Enforcement Service	X		
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X		
8	Dynamic Pricing Service	X		
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X		

Table 5 - Services tested in the pilots

ITS (Service)		Pilot				
		Barcelona	Antwerp	Paris	Wattens	Gdynia
1	Traffic Forecasting		X			X
2	Parking Occupancy Prediction	X	X	X	X	X
3	Multimodal Service		X			X
4	Guidance and Recommendation Service		X	X	X	X
5	Automatic Payment Service					X
6	Automatic Enforcement Service					X
7	Sustainable Traffic Model	X	X	X	X	X
8	Dynamic Pricing Service					X
9	Anomaly Detector Service	X	X	X	X	X

Full details of the service operation in real conditions will be provided in the deliverable D5.1. Further details are available upon request for the time being.

5. Conclusions

Fastprk2 is an applied project, whose results' validation relies on the successful operation of different pilots all around Europe. In this deliverable, the operational details of these pilots are provided, showing tangible evidence that the installed prototypes are successfully operating at the time of this writing. The gathered data and the acquired knowledge will be used to reach the desired maturity level of the final prototype by the end of the project, which will be ready for the market launch. Details of the pilots' results are not given here, but in the deliverable D5.1.

Abbreviations

Acronym

API
D
EC
EC-GA
ITS
M
MS
SME
TRL
WP

Full name

Application Programming Interface
Deliverable
European Commission
Grant Agreement
Intelligent Transport Services
Month
Milestone
Small - Medium Enterprise
Technology Readiness Level
Work package

Annexes

In the next pages, images of the pilots are provided covering from the exact location, the installation stage and evidence of the data acquired with the new sensors. Further details are available upon request.

Annex I. UPC Pilot (Barcelona, Spain)

Location images (satellite & photos)

Pilot area (general view)

Civil work at the pilot location

Installation Process (sensors and gateway)

Public Notice

Operational Details

Info tool showing real-time sector status (red - no parking available, green - free parking available)

Info tool showing real-time sensor status (red - no parking available, green - free parking available)

Tool showing floating window with real time occupancy data

Annex II. ENGIE Pilot (Antwerp, Belgium)

Civil work at the pilot location

Installation Process (sensors and gateway)

Public Notice

Operational Details

Info tool showing real-time sector status (red - no parking available, green - free parking available)

Info tool showing real-time sensor status (red - no parking available, green - free parking available)

Zone 1

Zone 2

Annex III. SWARCO Pilot (Wattens, Austria)

Google Maps screenshot (satellite)

Installed sensors

This pilot is located in private facilities with the primary purpose to test the reliability of the new sensor under adverse conditions (cold and snow). Since SWARCO is a direct competitor of Worldsensing in the field of Mobility, the access to proprietary software has been restricted as much as possible.

Annex IV. AFAPARK Pilot (Paris, France)

This combines sensors with the new Fastprk2 concept and old devices based on the commercial Fastprk alternative. The final goal is to compare the step forward in the performances achieved with the new technology. Fastprk2 sensors are indicated with a yellow spot.

Civil work at the pilot location

Installation Process (sensors and gateway)

Public Notice

Annex V. Fastprk2: communication with the pilots' partners (example)

Fastprk2 _ kick-off of the pilot and validation stage

49 mensajes

Francisco Hernandez <fhernandez@worldsensing.com> 9 de octubre de 2017, 12:02
 Darrasua, maria.martin@unio.edu; fcastek@fib.unio.edu;

We are pleased to inform you that the EU-funded project Fastprk2 has entered the pilot and validation stage.

First of all, I would like to personally thank you for your willingness to participate in the Fastprk2 pilots. Your involvement is of great value to Worldsensing since you are one of the key partners who will have the opportunity to test a unique solution in the market: an advanced parking sensor based on a double-detection technology (magnetic and I/R detection capabilities) and an innovative communication system (LoRa protocol). Moreover, your contribution will help us perfect the new Fastprk2 Parking Management System and to achieve the objectives set by the European Commission (EC) for 2020.

Worldsensing will conduct field trials of the new Fastprk2 system in real-world environments in collaboration with European partners and stakeholders who will be among the first promoters of the parking management system. Planned activities will include:

- *Conducting trials based on defined scenarios and under a variety of conditions (i.e. weather, rotation frequency, etc.);*
- *Gathering and archiving trial data and reconfiguring equipment and prototypes when changing scenario;*
- *Analyzing data to demonstrate the benefits of the Fastprk2 system and its application in multiple scenarios; and*
- *Tweaking scenario designs and deployments and fixing emerging issues in line with the defined contingency plan.*

Today, I would like to inform you about your rights and obligations with regards to participating in an EU project like Fastprk2.

Now that you have been approved by the European Commission, we would like to officially confirm that you are invited to take part in a pilot with no cost to you, which will include the deployment of next-generation parking sensors on your premises and the test of new traffic and parking services.

Worldsensing will bear all costs (previously agreed with each participant in the pilot) arising as operating expenses on the condition that they are actual, auditable and directly linked to the pilot. In return, you will be bound to clearly indicate the locations where you will install Fastprk2 and will need to acknowledge the support received from the EU. Besides, you will need to provide a feedback report sharing your experience with Fastprk2 as end-user and will need to answer any potential queries from EC services.

Please note that in line with current regulations you have 15 days after the receipt of this communication to confirm or withdraw your final participation in the Fastprk2 pilot project. Not replying will be considered agreeing to take part. In any case, we would appreciate a rapid response.

Upon receipt of your confirmation, we will contact you immediately to define the scope and timings of your project and will answer any questions you may have. You will find the project agenda with tentative dates in the attachment.

Please do not hesitate to get in touch with any questions you may have.

Thank you again for your interest in our project.

With kind regards,

Dr Francisco Hernández-Ramírez
 Fastprk2 Project Coordinator
 Worldsensing

[END OF THE DOCUMENT]